

A HYBRID STRENGTHENING SYSTEM USING CFRP AND FE-SMA FOR SEISMICALLY DEFICIENT RC COLUMNS

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ABSTRACT

This research explores a new hybrid seismic strengthening system applied to seismically deficient reinforced concrete (RC) bridge columns through utilizing Iron-based Shape Memory Alloy (Fe-SMA) vertical plates and Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymers (CFRP) jacket. Three RC circular bridge columns are constructed with poor ductility, and then two of them are strengthened with the aforementioned materials. The seismic performance of the columns is assessed in terms of strength, energy absorption, displacement capacity and experienced damages. This research indicates that Fe-SMA vertical plates with CFRP jackets considerably increase the column's lateral strength, energy absorption and displacement capacity and suppress damages.

KEYWORDS

Seismic, strengthening, hybrid, Shape Memory Alloy, ductility, lateral, bridge.

INTRODUCTION

The causes of vulnerability of reinforced concrete (RC) bridges to earthquakes has been an interesting topic for researchers. Such interest has been driven by numerous devastating worldwide earthquakes, including the collapse of several RC bridges, such as the 1994 Northridge earthquake, the 1995 Kobe Japan earthquake, and the 1989 Loma Prieta earthquake. Researchers investigated the reasons behind RC bridge collapses and concluded that the latter is attributed to the poor ductility and insufficient lateral strength of the RC bridges' supporting columns (Paulay and Priestley, 1992). Those deficiencies are caused by the inadequate design and detailing of RC bridge columns' internal reinforcements, including the large spacing of transverse reinforcements, thus, favouring the concrete core's early crush. Moreover, the insufficient lap splice length of the longitudinal reinforcements hindered the latter from developing a stable hysteretic behaviour through yielding. As a result, such practices were prohibited, and new seismic guidelines were issued to construct seismically resilient bridge columns.

Correspondingly, some RC bridge columns are considered seismically deficient and can trigger the collapse of the bridge during earthquakes. As a result, researchers have been developing seismic strengthening systems to enhance RC bridge columns' seismic performance. The strengthening systems mostly included the use of steel and concrete jackets. However, after the popularity of Fibre Reinforced Polymers (FRP) in the 1980s, researchers exploited the latter's benefits in the seismic strengthening of RC columns. In the 2000s, researchers incorporated another innovative material to strengthen RC columns: Shape Memory Alloy (SMA), known for their smart and super-elastic behaviour. The next section provides a brief background to define FRP and SMA and sheds light on recent research works that used both materials in the seismic strengthening of RC columns.

BRIEF DEFINITIONS OF FRP AND SMA

Fibre Reinforced Polymers (FRP) mainly consist of two components: fibres and resin, in which fibres carry the load, whereas the resin binds the fibres together and provides stiffness for the composite. Different fibres are used, such as carbon, glass, aramid, basalt, etc., in which the selection of fibre is critically affected by several factors, such as subjected loads (static or dynamic), the existence of fatigue and/or creep, environmental exposures, and costs. In addition, the FRP is known for its high strength-to-weight ratio, durability, and brittleness due to its perfectly elastic behaviour up to failure. Shape Memory Alloy (SMA) is a unique group of alloys that contains a combination of many elements such

as Nickel (Ni), Titanium (Ti), Iron (Fe), Silicone (Si), Copper (Cu), and many more. The SMA possesses distinctive thermomechanical properties, which are shape memory effect (SME) and superelasticity (SE) (Lagoudas, 2008). Such properties result from crystallographic transformations between austenite (A) and martensite (M), as shown in Figure 1. When heated to temperatures above the austenite finish temperature, A_f , the SMA acquires a fully austenitic structure. As represented in Figure 1, the austenitic SMA behaves superelastic in which all deformations are recovered when stresses disappear. On the other side, the SMA acquires a fully martensitic structure when cooled to temperatures below martensite finish temperature, M_f . At this stage, SMA can experience significant deformations, but a large portion of the latter remains permanent. However, such deformations are fully recovered when the SMA is heated above A_f . This phenomenon is called the “Shape Memory Effect” of SMA, which has been exploited by researchers to induce prestressing effects in the SMA by restraining the latter while heating. This prestress is usually termed the “recovery stress” of SMA and can reach 400-900 MPa, depending on the SMA alloy composition (Janke et al., 2005). The crystallographic transformation temperatures of SMA greatly depend on the latter’s alloy composition, which must be selected based on the purpose of application and the existing climatic conditions.

Figure 1: Stress-strain behaviour of SMA at both Austenite and Martensite

INCORPORATING SMA AND FRP IN PREVIOUS STUDIES AS A HYBRID SYSTEM

SMA and FRP have been used as a hybrid strengthening system to enhance the seismic performance of deficient RC columns. For instance, Shin and Andrawes (2011) used a hybrid confining jacket made from Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) sheet and NiTi SMA spiral wires. They reported a significant increase in the column’s flexural ductility and drift capacity. Miralami et al., (2019) used NiTi SMA vertical rebars to reinforce a CFRP (Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer) confined concrete jacket applied around the RC column. The authors showed that the strengthened column exhibited a reliable increase in lateral strength, energy dissipation capacity, and ductility. On the other side, Xing et al., (2020) strengthened RC columns with Near Surface Mounted (NSM) vertical SMA rebars and CFRP jackets. The authors reported a limited enhancement in the column’s flexural behaviour due to pull-out of the SMA rebars. However, the CFRP jacket provided a considerable increase in the column’s energy absorption capacity.

MATERIAL PROPERTIES OF FRP AND SMA USED

In this research, SikaWrap Hex-230C, a unidirectional carbon fibre fabric, is used to confine the deficient RC columns. On the other hand, the Iron-based SMA (Fe-SMA) plate supplied by Re-fer AG in a 2% pre-strained condition is used as external vertical reinforcement on each side of the column (more details are provided in the following sections) and is then heated above A_f (150 to 300°C) (Shahverdi et al., 2018). The other activation temperatures M_f , M_s , and A_s were reported to be -90°C, -75°C, and 85°C, respectively (Dong et al. 2009). The material properties of the CFRP and Fe-SMA materials are illustrated in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

Table 1: SikaWrap Hex-230C CFRP material properties (Sika Canada, 2023)

Material	Thickness (mm)	Width (mm)	Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)*	Tensile Strength (MPa)*	Tensile Elongation (%)*
CFRP	0.38	610	74.7	801	1.01

* Based on 24 sample coupons

Table 2: Re-plate Fe-SMA material properties (Shahverdi et al., 2018)

Material	Thickness (mm)	Width (mm)	Modulus of Elasticity (GPa) ¹	Tensile Strength (MPa) ²	Yield Stress (MPa) ²	Tensile Elongation (%) ²	Pre-Strain Level (%)	Permanent Elongation After Releasing (%)	Activation Temperature (A _n) (°C)	Recovery Stress (MPa) ³
Fe-SMA	1.5	120	75	980	523	45	2	1.25	150-300	393

¹: Based on 51 sample coupons pre-strained to 0.5, 1, 2, 4, and 6%

²: Based on 9 sample coupons

³: Based on 6 sample coupons pre-strained to 2% and heated in air

COLUMN DESIGN AND LOADING SETUP

Column specimens

Three large-scale single cantilever RC columns of diameter 300 mm and clear height 1600 mm are constructed. All columns are supported on square 600 mm thick RC foundations of side length 1450 mm. The RC columns are considered seismically deficient due to insufficient transverse reinforcements (i.e. hoops) provided at 150 mm spacing. Meanwhile, the Canadian Bridge Code imposes that hoop spacing should not exceed 75 mm (CSA S6, 2019). As for the longitudinal reinforcements, the columns are reinforced with 8-20M bars (diameter of 20mm), thus representing a 3.39% reinforcement ratio. A schematic drawing of a single RC column is shown in Figure 2. The average yield strength of columns' longitudinal reinforcements and lateral hoops is 420 MPa, and the average compressive strength of concrete at the age of testing is 34.5 MPa and 30 MPa for the columns and the foundations, respectively.

Figure 2: Schematic drawing of the RC columns specimen

Testing setup

All RC columns are subjected to a quasi-static lateral cyclic loading applied at their top. The lateral load is applied through a displacement-controlled hydraulic actuator. In addition, a 160 kN vertical load is applied at the top of the columns to simulate gravity effects while resisting seismic loadings. The 160 kN represents 5% of the columns' concrete gross compressive strength and is also applied with a displacement-controlled hydraulic actuator. A roller support is placed between the columns and the vertical actuator to allow the lateral displacement of the columns.

Loading protocol

The quasi-static lateral cyclic load adopted in this study is presented in Figure 3. The loading protocol is initiated with two cycles at each of 0.5, 0.75, 1.5, and 3 mm deflections at a rate of 0.25 mm/sec. Then, a deflection increment of 3 mm is applied until reaching 12 mm. After that, the deflection increment and the loading rate increase to 8 mm and 0.75 mm/sec, respectively, until reaching 68 mm deflection, such that three cycles are applied at each targeted deflection. Further, the latter and the former increase to 15 mm and 1.25 mm/sec until failure, with two cycles applied at each deflection.

Figure 3: Quasi-Static cyclic loading protocol

RETROFITTING SCHEMES

Column confinement

The first RC column is left unstrengthened for comparison purposes. The second column is flexurally strengthened with vertical Fe-SMA plates only (labelled as FlexSMA). Finally, the third column is confined with a CFRP jacket and flexurally strengthened with Fe-SMA vertical plates (labelled as FlexSMA-ConfCFRP). The number of CFRP jacket layers is selected to be two, which generates a 4 MPa confining pressure, and is determined such that the drift and ductility requirements of the CSA S6-2019 are both satisfied.

Anchorage of the flexural strengthening elements

To enhance the flexural strength and behaviour of the deficient columns in this study, vertical Fe-SMA plates are utilized on both sides of the column. The bottom of the Fe-SMA is welded to a steel base plate bolted to the foundation through 6 cast-in anchors that are embedded 210 mm in the foundation. On the other hand, the top of the Fe-SMA is bolted to the RC column through 4 to 6 (depending on the needed anchorage strength) post-installed 80 mm deep wedge anchors. The weld at the bottom of the Fe-SMA consists of two longitudinal weld lines that are 230 mm long and then 120 mm transverse weld to cover the entire width of the Fe-SMA plate. The anchorage system is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4(a): Cast-in anchors embedded in the foundation

Figure 4(b): Fe-SMA bottom welded to steel base plate

Figure 4(c): Column flexural strengthening elements on RC column

Figure 4(d): Fe-SMA wedge anchors

To enhance the strength of the Fe-SMA bolted connection with the RC column such that concrete breakout is avoided, the middle top of all strengthened columns is wrapped with two layers of CFRP, which is the same amount provided for confining the plastic hinge region of column 3 (FlexSMA-ConfCFRP).

Activating Fe-SMAs through high temperature

After installing the Fe-SMAs on both sides of columns 2 and 3, the Fe-SMAs are heated to temperatures above 200°C using a flame torch (Figure 5(a)). Several thermocouples and high temperature-resistant

strain gauges are attached to the Fe-SMAs and are shown in Figure 5(b). The maximum temperatures reached by the Fe-SMAs for columns 2 and 3 are about 350°C and 250°C, respectively, which indicates that all Fe-SMAs transitioned to a fully austenitic structure. Since the Fe-SMAs are restrained from both ends, recovery stress is developed due to their SME, as the Fe-SMAs tend to retract and recover the initial 2% factory pre-strain. The strain gauges attached to the Fe-SMAs recorded low values, indicating some prestress losses while heating the Fe-SMAs. The strain values ranged from 500 to 1,200 micro-strains, giving almost 40 to 80 MPa prestress loss, respectively. Cyclic tests were conducted several days after all the Fe-SMAs acquired room temperatures (21.7°C).

Figure 5(a): Heating the Fe-SMA plate with a torch

Thermocouple#1

Thermocouple#2

Strain Gauge#1

Strain Gauge#2

Figure 5(b): Temperature and strain monitoring instruments on the Fe-SMA plate

TESTING MATRIX

As described earlier, three RC columns are tested under quasi-static cyclic lateral loading to assess their seismic performance. The first column is kept unstrengthened. The second column, FlexSMA, is flexurally strengthened with vertical Fe-SMA plates and wrapped with CFRP at its upper half to enhance the anchorage strength. The third column, FlexSMA-ConfCFRP, includes vertical Fe-SMA plates and two layers of CFRP confinement applied along its entire height. The three columns are presented in Figure 6. The columns are painted white to apply a random speckle pattern for the Digital Image Correlation Testing (DICT) and ease of crack monitoring during the cyclic test.

Figure 6(a): Unstrengthened (Column 1)

Figure 6(b): FlexSMA (Column 2)

Figure 6(c): FlexSMA-ConfCFRP (Column 3)

TEST RESULTS

Hysteretic behaviour

The hysteretic behaviour of all three columns is shown in Figure 7. The unstrengthened column exhibited a stable hysteretic behaviour until the onset of yielding of the internal steel, which occurred in the 18th cycle at 26.36 mm lateral displacement (1.8% drift). Similarly, the FlexSMA column and the FlexSMA-ConfCFRP column recorded similar yield displacements of 26.52 mm (1.8%) and 26.08 mm (1.7%), respectively. The unstrengthened column reached its nominal (i.e. maximum) capacity at 52

mm lateral displacement (3.5% drift). After that, the latter experienced strength degradation until it failed at 98 mm lateral displacement (6.6% drift) due to its longitudinal steel rebars buckling excessively in both directions and due to its complete loss of the concrete core.

Figure 7(a): Force-Displacement curve for unstrengthened column

Figure 7(b): Force-Displacement curve for FlexSMA column

Figure 7(c): Force-Displacement curve for FlexSMA- ConfCFRP column

Figure 7(d): Backbone curve for all columns

For the FlexSMA column, the nominal load reached is at 60 mm lateral displacement (4.1% drift). However, the latter still exhibited stable hysteretic behaviour even after hitting its nominal capacity while experiencing minimal strength degradation. The test was eventually stopped at 126 mm lateral displacement (8.5% drift) due to the limitations of the hydraulic actuator's stroke. The FlexSMA column still possessed its structural integrity at the end of the test due to the elastic behaviour of the Fe-SMA plates in enhancing the self-centering ability and displacement capacity of the column. On the other hand, the FlexSMA-ConfCFRP column reached nominal load at 98 mm lateral displacement (6.6% drift), then remained stable until experiencing a sharp drop in strength at 126 mm lateral displacement (8.5% drift) due to the rupture of the Fe-SMA plate on one side of the column. The FlexSMA-ConfCFRP column, as shown in Figure 7(c), maintained a superior hysteretic behaviour in which strength and stiffness degradations were insignificant until the Fe-SMA plate ruptured at the welding location on the base anchor. This behaviour is mainly attributed to the CFRP confinement in hindering the early crushing of the column's concrete core, thus, providing the column with a little enhancement in displacement capacity, which was eventually interrupted by the rupture of the Fe-SMA plate that happened in the third cycle of 126 mm lateral displacements. The lateral strain in the CFRP reached beyond 1,010 micro-strains; however, its rupture did not occur. In Figure 7(c), after the Fe-SMA ruptured, the test continued to another five cycles at 126 mm lateral displacement. Interestingly, no further strength and stiffness degradation was shown by the cycles overlapping each other. This explains that the CFRP wrap acted as a second line of defence when the Fe-SMA plate ruptured under high stresses. Also, in Figure 7(d), the column's lateral strength dropped from 135 kN to 102 kN when the Fe-SMA ruptured, which is almost the same strength as the unstrengthened column. Therefore, the authors of this paper strongly believe that the FlexSMA-ConfCFRP column can still go beyond 126

mm displacement without a significant strength degradation due to the ability of the CFRP jacket in providing the column with a further substantial increase in displacement capacity.

Lateral strength and displacement capacity

The nominal and ultimate capacities of all columns are shown in Table 3. The nominal strength of the column is defined as the maximum load recorded, whereas the ultimate strength is taken as the first load recorded after the column loses at least 15% of its nominal strength.

The unstrengthened column recorded a nominal strength of 97.9 and -85.1 kN in the pull and push direction, respectively. However, after utilizing the vertical Fe-SMA plates in the FlexSMA column, the lateral strength increased by 35.45% on average compared to the unstrengthened column. Moreover, when the CFRP jacket was applied on the third column FlexSMA-ConfCFRP, the enhancement in strength was minimal (around 1% increase compared to column FlexSMA), which is expected since the CFRP jacket does not have any flexural contribution to the column. Such an increase in strength in both columns is mainly attributed to the elastic behaviour and high strength of the applied Fe-SMA plates.

On the other hand, column FlexSMA experienced a 20% increase in the ultimate displacement compared to the unstrengthened column, which is an outstanding enhancement for a column without any confinement effects. Similarly, the FlexSMA-ConfCFRP column recorded a similar increase in displacement capacity. This indicates that the ductile behaviour of the Fe-SMA plates aided the column in attaining higher ultimate displacements. This is attributed to the ductile behaviour of the Fe-SMA and its significant contribution in enhancing the self-centering ability and displacement capacity of the RC column. However, as described in the previous section, the presence of the CFRP jackets prevented the failure of the column in which the latter can still experience further displacements, thus, recording much more enhancement in the column's displacement capacity.

Table 3: Nominal and ultimate capacity of all tested RC columns

Specimen	Pull (+ve)				Push (-ve)			
	Nominal load (kN)	Nominal disp. (mm)	Ultimate load (kN)	Ultimate disp. (mm)	Nominal load (kN)	Nominal disp. (mm)	Ultimate load (kN)	Ultimate disp. (mm)
Unstrengthened	97.9	83	86.3	113	-85.1	-52	-75	-98
FlexSMA	129.6	83	118.9	126	-118	-60	-109.6	-126
FlexSMA-ConfCFRP	135.9	98	102.3	124.5	-114	-98	-93.5	-126

Hysteretic energy

The hysteretic energy defines the ability of the column to absorb seismic energy through lateral displacement. It is obtained as the cumulative area enclosed within the hysteretic curves of the RC columns. Figure 8 shows a comparison of the hysteretic energy dissipated between all three columns. The unstrengthened column dissipated the least energy of 18 kJ. However, utilizing the proposed strengthening systems, whether Fe-SMA plates or Fe-SMA plates with CFRP jackets, significantly increased the columns' energy dissipation capacity, which reached a 40.35% increase on average. Such an increase is attributed to the high deformation ability of the Fe-SMA plates. The latter can experience 45% elongations, which is more than double the steel's ultimate elongation, thus, allowing both columns 2 and 3 to possess a stable hysteretic behaviour characterized by a slow degradation in strength and stiffness. Moreover, the increase in hysteretic energy is also attributed to the enhanced recentring ability of the columns due to the prestressing effect of the Fe-SMAs. Also, the CFRP wraps contributed to enhancing the hysteretic energy of column 3 since the latter confined the column's core and hindered its crush at the early stages of loading.

As a result, this illustrates the potential of both proposed strengthening systems in providing seismically deficient RC columns with an enhanced ability to dissipate significant seismic energy before failure. Moreover, the results showed that Fe-SMA plates hold great potential in enhancing the flexural strength and energy dissipation of deficient RC columns due to their high deformation capacity and their

prestressing effect through simple heat activation, which is a process that is extremely hard to achieve with conventional steel material due to complexity of the prestressing systems.

Figure 8: Energy dissipated by each RC column

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, it is observed that Fe-SMA plates successfully increase the lateral strength and displacement capacity of seismically deficient RC columns. Further, applying a CFRP jacket to the column protects the column against concrete core crush and buckling of the longitudinal reinforcements. The newly proposed hybrid strengthening system, which includes the first attempt of using Fe-SMA plates to enhance the flexural strength and behaviour of RC columns, can potentially protect the column against strong earthquakes due to the complementary action achieved by the Fe-SMA plates and the CFRP jacket. The hybrid strengthening system enhances and prolongs the energy dissipation capacity and increases the column's lateral strength. Moreover, the anchorage system adopted in this study is deemed successful since the concrete breakout, pry-out, and pull-out of the bolts are all avoided. Besides, the weld applied at the bottom of the Fe-SMA plates successfully resisted the high stresses attained by the Fe-SMA plates. This newly proposed anchorage system could eliminate all slippage and anchorage failure problems reported by other researchers who attempted to use SMA for the flexural strengthening of RC columns.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

CITATIONS

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